

DISPERSAL AND POPULATION DYNAMICS OF THE NEW ENGLAND AMERICAN OYSTERCATCHER (*HAEMATOPUS PALLIATUS*)

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Abstract

Dispersal is a crucial ecological process that drives such processes as range expansion and colonization. Since the early 1900's the breeding range of the American Oystercatcher, *Haematopus palliatus*, has expanded north along the Atlantic Coast. Since the 1970's the species has assumed a prominent role as a nesting shorebird along the Atlantic Coast including Cape Cod, Massachusetts and the surrounding islands. We examined the productivity and movement of a population of oystercatchers from 2005-2007 in Nantucket County, Massachusetts. From 2005 to 2007, a total of 144 oystercatchers (100 adults, 44 juveniles) were individually marked using a coded color band. Movement during the breeding season and persistence of oystercatchers at nesting grounds were recorded for marked individuals. Auxiliary markings continue to provide new information about nest site fidelity and have the potential to provide information about the population dynamics of the oystercatcher in Massachusetts. Of the 67 adults marked in 2005-2006, 43 (64.2%) have been resighted during the non-breeding season in an array of sites throughout the accepted winter distribution. In 2006, 20 of 26 marked adults returned to their respected beaches in Nantucket County, which supports a characteristic often assumed for the American Oystercatcher, breeding site fidelity. This measure of fidelity (or return rate) can be used as an early, baseline estimate of adult survival. Based on this mark-resight model for estimating return rate, adult survival is ≥ 0.77 (0.084 SE).

Introduction

During the first three decades of the twentieth century, the American Oystercatcher was an uncommon visitor to the Atlantic Coast north of Virginia (Post and Raynor 1964). In the past three decades, the American Oystercatcher has become a common nesting shorebird as far north as Massachusetts. The first oystercatchers observed in Massachusetts were in 1969 on the island of Martha's Vineyard (Finch 1970, Veit and Petersen 1993). After the first recorded nest on Martha's Vineyard, breeding pairs were observed on Tuckernuck Island and Monomoy Island in the following year (Veit and Petersen 1993). Currently in Massachusetts, the number of

breeding oystercatchers continues to rise, reaching 200 pairs in 2007 (Fig. 1), of which 109 pairs nested in Nantucket and Dukes Counties (Melvin, personal communication).

As the American Oystercatcher continues to expand its range and abundance in the Northeast United States (US), there is inadequate knowledge about the biology of this shorebird with respect to dispersal, philopatry, habitat requirements, and survival. Furthermore, recent evidence shows this species of bird is declining (Davis et al. 2001) and has recently been named as a species of “High Concern” in the US Shorebird Conservation Plan (Brown et al. 2001). With efficient trapping techniques and a standard protocol for color banding created by the American Oystercatcher Working Group (AOWG) in 2004, a species-wide color banded population is currently being established along the Atlantic Coast. Currently, ongoing AOWG projects occur in six US states: Massachusetts, New Jersey, Virginia, North Carolina, South Carolina, and Georgia.

The primary objective of this study was to examine the life history, movement, and population dynamics of the American Oystercatcher on the islands of Nantucket County (Nantucket, Tuckernuck, and Muskeget Islands) and Dukes County (Martha’s Vineyard and Chappaquiddick Island). Upon completion, this study will provide necessary information to the Massachusetts Division of Fisheries and Wildlife for current issues involving beach management and conservation of the American Oystercatcher and other beach nesting birds. This study has been conducted over the past three years (2005-2007). In 2007, we examined the following:

1. Estimate nesting and fledgling success of American Oystercatchers in Nantucket County, Massachusetts from 1 April through 15 September 2007. Compare these estimates to concurrent studies in Massachusetts, New Jersey, North Carolina, and South Carolina.
2. Establish a marked population of oystercatchers to examine annual survival and movement during the breeding season and subsequent migration.
3. Construct a demographic model and apply estimated demographic rates in order to examine the dynamics of the local population.

Methods

The study was conducted on the islands of Massachusetts approximately 25 - 35 km south of Cape Cod, including Nantucket, Tuckernuck, Muskeget, Martha’s Vineyard, and Chappaquiddick (Fig. 2). These islands are formed of glacial moraine, contains extensive marshes and shorelines of sandy beaches, which are primary habitat for the American Oystercatcher (Lauro and Burger 1989, Humphrey 1990).

All estimates of nesting productivity will be generated from data collected in Nantucket County. This site was selected because close monitoring of nests and young is collected by a crew of researchers that increases the precision and accuracy of the data. During the month of May, weekly visits were made to the breeding grounds on Tuckernuck, until field researchers continuously stayed on Nantucket and Tuckernuck from 25 May - 25 August collect nesting productivity of breeding oystercatchers. When an active nest was located, the number of eggs and GPS location were recorded. Additional data collected included: nest substrate, surrounding

vegetation, and distance from the high tide line. All nest sites were visited a minimum of three times per week until the nest failed or young fledged.

Once a breeding pair of adult oystercatchers had been identified, the adults were trapped using a decoy, sound system, and leg-hold noose mats (McGowan and Simons 2005). During the 2007 breeding season, alternate trapping techniques were exhaustively tested as an approach to increase trapping efficiency including: mist net, spot dip net, box trap, and walk-in trap. None of these alternative techniques proved to be as efficient as the decoy trap technique.

Additional oystercatchers were color banded on Martha's Vineyard, Chappaquiddick Island, and Ram Island (Mattapoisett, Massachusetts). Each bird was fitted with a USFWS metal band and coded Darvic-plastic color band from Haggie Engraving, Inc. that is field readable. Juvenile birds were captured by hand to ensure the safety of young birds. All young were captured between 21-35 days. The age range was employed to serve three functions: 1) AOWG protocol states that the leg of a juvenile is large enough to fit the bands after 10 days of age, 2) prior to fledging, the young are easily captured to reduce stress, and 3) with a finite number of band combinations, the delaying of capture until a minimum of 21 days of age increases the probability of fledging success. A 2-3 breast feathers were collected for an anticipated study of the population genetics of the Massachusetts oystercatcher and measurements were recorded for every trapped bird including: tarsus, wing chord, exposed bill length, head length. In addition to morphometrics, digital images were taken of the eye of each individual as well as plumage contrasts found on the back and scapulars.

Results

Color banding

In 2006, 33 adults and 26 juveniles were trapped and uniquely marked (Table 1). Movements during the breeding season and persistence of oystercatchers at nesting grounds were recorded for marked individuals.

After three years, the efforts of this project have resulted in 100 adult and 44 juvenile oystercatchers color banded on the islands of Massachusetts (Table 1). For a more detailed report of banding location, see Table 1. With each newly reported resight and the continuation of color banding in Massachusetts, this project has the capacity to elucidate many biological processes in the migratory American Oystercatcher of New England, including a heightened resolution of migratory patterns and the estimation of individual-based survival and productivity parameters.

Based on nest monitoring, there were 67 breeding pairs of adult American Oystercatchers observed in Nantucket County (51-Nantucket, 13-Tuckernuck, and 3-Muskeget). A total of 27 chicks fledged, and the productivity of Nantucket County was 0.403 young fledged per nesting pair.

Nantucket and Muskeget Islands are in close proximity to Tuckernuck, and oystercatchers have been observed traveling from island to island during the summer. With the help of a field

assistant employed through the Nantucket Conservation Foundation for the second year, additional adult oystercatchers were trapped and banded on Muskeget, Nantucket, and Martha's Vineyard in 2007 to better detect movement of breeding birds through the breeding season, into the fall, and winter range.

Post-breeding resights

All oystercatchers that spend the breeding season in Massachusetts and north must migrate south for the winter months. Of the 67 adults marked in 2005 and 2006, 43 (64.2%) have been resighted during the non-breeding season (Table 2). Of the 18 color-banded juveniles, only four (22.2%) individuals were resighted, all of which were located on Nantucket and Monomoy, MA (Table 2).

Of the 67 marked adult oystercatchers, 49 (73.1%) were observed in a staging population approximately 20 km northeast of Nantucket on Monomoy Island / South Beach, Chatham (MISB) (Fig. 2, Fig. 4). The MISB system is known to have upwards of 200 oystercatchers using this site as a pre-migration staging area (Schulte et al. 2006), and is one of the largest non-breeding sites in the Northeastern US. The location of this staging population is a result of the abundant bivalve population created by the extensive tidal flats in the surrounding area (Harrington, personal communication).

Marked wintering oystercatchers have been observed in an array of sites throughout the accepted winter distribution, excluding one marked adult observed for part of the 2006/2007 winter on Long Island, New York (Table 2, Fig. 4). With the exception of the occasional small winter population north of Ocean County, NJ (Murphy unpublished data), these individuals are thought to migrate primarily to the coasts of Virginia (Humphrey 1990, Nol and Humphrey 1994). Uniquely marking oystercatchers breeding in Massachusetts has provided evidence against these earlier studies. In fact, Massachusetts oystercatchers appear to be wintering throughout all of the East Coast and Gulf Coast (Fig. 4). Auxiliary markings are providing new information about the persistence of breeding oystercatchers at nesting grounds as well as providing information about the dynamics of a migrating population.

In 2006, 20 (77%) adult marked birds returned to their respected island in Nantucket County, which raises support to a characteristic often assumed for the American Oystercatcher, breeding philopatry. This breeding site fidelity supports the concept that the migratory oystercatchers of these islands may behave as a metapopulation system. In other words, each local population may cycle independent of the other surrounding islands but interact at some level via dispersal. Furthermore, this measure of site fidelity (or return rate) can be used as an early, baseline estimate of adult survival. Based on the mark-resight model for estimating return rate, adult survival is ≥ 0.77 (0.084 SE). With every resight and the continuation of establishing a color banded population in Massachusetts, this research has the capacity to elucidate many biological processes in the migratory American Oystercatcher of Massachusetts, including a heightened resolution of movement patterns and the estimation of individual-based survival and productivity parameters.

Construction of a population model

Demographic stage-structured modeling methods will be used to investigate the breeding population of oystercatchers in Nantucket County (Fig. 5). Based on the data collected, this local population has dramatically increased over the study period, and the model will be used to explore the potential reasons for this rise in breeding pairs. More specifically, this model will investigate the influence of (1) a high variability in annual survivorship, and (2) immigration (*I*) into the local population.

This model may prove to be a potential tool for management groups that conduct annual breeding shorebird censuses. It is important to reiterate a model such as this has offered some insight on a local population of shorebirds, but not without making several assumptions in the life-cycle and parameter estimations. With the continuation of data collection on the life history characteristics such as annual survival, fertility, and movement, this model may serve as a foundation for examining population fluctuations and immigration. A model of this type could be a useful tool for state management and conservation organizations located in the migratory zone. More importantly, a model including inter-season movement for different classes may be useful to better understand the species throughout its current range.

Presentation of study results

Preliminary results of the research collected from 2005-2007 and the population model were presented at the *2007 Eastern Bird Banding Association Conference* in Brewster, Massachusetts; the *2007 and 2005 MassWildlife Tern and Plover Meeting* in Hyannis, Massachusetts; the *2007 and 2005 Nantucket Biodiversity Initiative* in Nantucket, Massachusetts; the *2006 and 2005 American Oystercatcher Working Group Meeting*; and *2006 Shorebird Science in the Western Hemisphere*, an international conference that took place in Boulder, Colorado.

Future suggestions

As mentioned earlier, with the continuation of color banding in Massachusetts and collection of resight observations, this project has the capacity to elucidate many biological processes in the migratory American Oystercatcher of New England, including a detailed understanding of migratory patterns and the estimation confounded demographic parameters such as adult and subadult survival. This work is dependent on the continuation of color banding in Nantucket County, as well as an expansion to include more of Martha's Vineyard, the Elizabeth Islands, and regions of Cape Cod.

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Tables and figures

Table 1. Ages (adult or juvenile) and total numbers of the 100 adult and 44 juvenile banded oystercatchers on the islands of Massachusetts from 2005-2007. Note-Martha's Vineyard and Chappaquiddick were not part of the 2005 study, and Ram Island in Mattapoissett was not part of the study from 2005-2006.

Island	2005		2006		2007		Total	
	Adult	Juv.	Adult	Juv.	Adult	Juv.	Adult	Juv.
Nantucket	7	0	25	7	18	17	50	24
Tuckernuck	15	1	6	4	1	4	22	9
Muskeget	4	0	2	0	2	0	8	0
Martha's Vineyard			4	2	3	2	7	4
Chappaquiddick			4	4	6	3	10	7
Ram					3	0	3	0
Total	26	1	41	17	33	26	100	44

Table 2. Total resight observations of marked oystercatchers from Massachusetts partitioned by state. Note, that Massachusetts total observations are from Monomoy Island / South Beach, Chatham.

Age	Site							
	Mass.	New York	New Jersey	Virginia	N. Carolina	S. Carolina	Georgia	Florida
Adult	39	1	3*	1*	*	*	*	*
Juvenile	4‡	0	0	*	1*	1*	2*	11*

*: represents incomplete data, but observations have been confirmed via personal communication

‡: one of these records is a unique recovery of a dead juvenile

Figure 1. Number of breeding pairs of oystercatchers in censused in Massachusetts from 1970-2006 with trendline (data taken from Humphrey 1990, Veit and Petersen 1993, Myers et al. 1998, and Melvin 2003, 2004, unpubl.).

Figure 2. Map of Cape Cod, Massachusetts and associated islands. Study area includes Martha's Vineyard, Chappaquiddick, Muskeget, Tuckernuck, and Nantucket.

Map created by S. Murphy from geodata provided by the Massachusetts Office of Geographic and Environmental Information (MassGIS).

Figure 3. Map of banding locations (insets) and resight observations (●) of marked oystercatchers along the Atlantic Coast from 2005-2007. Insets include three major concentrations in Massachusetts: Nantucket County, Martha's Vineyard, and Monomoy Island.

Map created by S. Murphy from geodata provided by the Massachusetts Office of Geographic and Environmental Information (MassGIS).

Figure 4. The life-cycle illustration of the American Oystercatcher with corresponding stage-structured projection matrix (A) and immigration matrix (I). Stages include juvenile (1), subadult (2), adult (3). Parameters included are: survival (P_i), transition (G_i), fecundity (F_i), and immigration (IMM).

$$A = \begin{bmatrix} 0 & 0 & F_3 \\ G_1 & P_2 & 0 \\ 0 & G_2 & P_3 \end{bmatrix}$$

$$I = \begin{bmatrix} 0 \\ 0 \\ IMM_t \end{bmatrix}$$